

Kinetics of Silver-Catalysed Oxidation of Propionamide by Potassium Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of propionamide by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been studied. The reaction is found to be first order w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. propionamide, but the specific rate is a function of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and propionamide concentration. It decreases with an increase in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ but increases with an increase in propionamide concentration and attains a maximum value at high concentration. The specific rate is linearly related to $[\text{Ag}^+]$ by an expression

$$k = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} + 0.78[\text{Ag}^+]$$

K^+ exerts a strong specific inhibitory effect on the rate. The temperature coefficient, energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation have been determined. The mole ratio is found to be 1 : 1 and the final products are $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$ and nitrogen. Traces of allyl acetate inhibit the reaction appreciably. On the basis of these kinetic results, a possible reaction mechanism has been proposed and the corresponding rate expression deduced.

A study of the kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl formamide¹ and formamide² by peroxydisulphate ion in presence of AgNO_3 has shown that the two reactions are similar in kinetic behaviour which suggested to us that probably different aliphatic amides undergo oxidation by peroxydisulphate ion by a similar mechanism. In order to substantiate this view and to decide the exact mechanism of these processes, the kinetics of oxidation of propionamide by $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ in presence of AgNO_3 as catalyst has now been carried out by us. A reference to literature shows that no previous kinetic study of this reaction seems to have been made. However, some preliminary work on the oxidation of acetamide and formamide by peroxydisulphate ion has been recently reported by Mushran and coworkers^{3,4}.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental technique used for following the progress of the reaction was the same as adopted in dimethyl formamide— $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ reaction¹.

RESULTS

Just like dimethyl-formamide reaction, the specific rate for propionamide oxidation in each kinetic run was evaluated by subtracting the specific rate of self decomposition of

$K_2S_2O_8$ from that of the total reaction. The kinetic data obtained at varying concentrations of the reactants are represented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 and the value of initial rate

FIG 1

($-dc/dt$) w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and w.r.t. $C_2H_5CONH_2$ (reactant whose concentration is varied) and the specific rate therefrom are tabulated below :

TABLE 1

$AgNO_3 = 0.001 M$		Temp. = 35°			
$[K_2S_2O_8] \times 10^2 M$	$[C_2H_5CONH_2] M$	$-dc/dt$	$k' \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'' \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.5	0.1	0.8393×10^{-4}	33.86	16.93	16.93
0.75	0.1	1.171×10^{-4}	28.78	14.39	14.39
1.00	0.1	1.515×10^{-4}	22.57	13.43	9.14
1.5	0.1	2.206×10^{-4}	17.71	12.12	5.59
2.0	0.1	2.857×10^{-4}	13.54	11.51	2.03
1.0	0.05	0.9803×10^{-2}	21.43	13.43	7.89
1.0	0.1	1.161×10^{-2}	22.57	13.43	9.14
1.0	0.2	1.351×10^{-2}	23.98	13.43	10.55
1.0	0.4	1.541×10^{-2}	25.58	13.43	12.15
1.0	0.8	1.851×10^{-2}	27.41	13.43	13.98

where k' and k'' are the first order rate constant for the overall reaction and for self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion respectively and $k = k' - k''$.

The specific rate is seen to be a function of the initial concentration of both $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $C_2H_5CONH_2$, being governed by the expressions

$$-\log k = 2.48 + 53.33[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0 \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$k = k_{max} \frac{[C_2H_5CONH_2]_0}{b + [C_2H_5CONH_2]_0} \quad \dots (2)$$

where b is a constant. In support of equation (2) a plot of $\frac{[C_2H_5CONH_2]_0}{k}$ vs $[C_2H_5CONH_2]_0$ was found to be linear from which k_{max} and b were evaluated as $15.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and 0.06 respectively. Using these values, the specific rate k for any initial concentration of

FIG 2

propionamide can be calculated with the help of equation (2) and compared with the experimental values. This comparison is found to be fairly good, as is borne out by the data of Table 2.

TABLE 2

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$; $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$; Temp. = 35°

$[C_2H_5CONH_2]_0M$	$k \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (experimental)	$k \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (calculated)
0.05	7.89	6.81
0.1	9.14	9.37
0.2	10.55	11.53
0.4	12.15	13.04
0.8	13.98	13.95

Using differential method, the mean value of order comes out to be 0.90 and 0.22 w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $C_2H_5CONH_2$ respectively.

Effect of $AgNO_3$ concentration: The catalytic effect of $AgNO_3$ is similar to that found in dimethyl formamide reaction and the following relationship is seen to be obeyed

$$k = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} + 0.78 C_{Ag^+}$$

Effect of Temperature: Table 3 gives the value of various activation parameters for this reaction.

TABLE 3

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01M$; $AgNO_3 = 0.001M$; $C_2H_5CONH_2 = 0.01M$

Temp. in $^\circ A$	$k \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Temp. coefficient	Energy of activation (E) in Kcals mole $^{-1}$	Frequency factor liter mole $^{-1}$ sec $^{-1}$ $A \times 10^{-6}$	Entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) e.u.	Free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) K Cals mole $^{-1}$
303	5.86			12.03	-28.16	24.69
308	9.14	2.39	16.44	12.13	-28.18	24.89
313	14.05	2.40	17.08	11.73	-28.28	24.98
318	22.04			12.15	-28.24	25.13
Mean		2.39	16.76	12.01	-28.21	24.92

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 16.48 \text{ Kcals mole}^{-1} \text{ (graphically).}$$

ΔH^\ddagger has been calculated by a plot of $\log \frac{k}{kT/h}$ vs $1/T$ on the basis of the equation

$K = \frac{kT}{h} \times e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT} \times e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$. The value of ΔH^\ddagger (16.48 K Cals mole $^{-1}$) has been used in the above equation to calculate ΔS^\ddagger .

The energy of activation for this reaction is found to be similar to that for the oxidation of dimethyl-formamide¹ and formamide². Furthermore, the entropy of activation in this reaction is also negative and of similar order of magnitude as for the oxidation of dimethyl-formamide¹ and formamide². These facts suggest that the mechanism for these reactions should be similar.

Since the reaction exhibits specific inhibitory effect, similar to that present in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ -dimethyl-formamide and $S_2O_8^{2-}$ -formamide reactions, the effect of ionic strength has not been investigated in detail, although it has been observed that the salt effect is negative and potassium ion exerts a strong specific inhibitory effect on the rate.

Effect of allyl acetate : The effect of traces of allyl acetate ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) on the rate of propionamide reaction and of self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion is represented together in Fig. 3. It is clear that the inhibitory effect on the two reactions is of similar order of magnitude, suggesting thereby that the radical (S) involved in self decomposition and in propionamide oxidation may be the same.

FIG-3

Mole ratio and analysis of products : The mole ratio, after taking into account the self decomposition of potassium peroxydisulphate, comes out to be one mole of potassium peroxydisulphate to one mole of propionamide. The presence of propionic acid throughout the course of reaction was detected by ferric chloride and amyl alcohol test. On the other hand the presence of ammonia tested by Riegler's reagent⁵ was detected in the early stages only but after 24 hrs ammonia was found to be absent, probably due to its oxidation to nitrogen. This suggests that propionic acid and ammonia are the initial products, probably due to the hydrolytic decomposition of propionamide, the latter being oxidised to nitrogen.

DISCUSSION

The close similarity in kinetic behaviour with the dimethyl-formamide¹ and formamide² reactions together with the fact that the mole ratio is one and propionic acid and nitrogen are the final products suggests to us that the following mechanism may be operative :

It is worthwhile to point out that the first two steps have been proposed by Bawn and Margerison⁶ and by Srivastava and coworkers in other silver ion catalysed oxidation reactions of different substrates by peroxydisulphate ion⁷⁻¹⁰ also.

Applying the steady state treatment to the radicals Ag^{2+} , $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot -}$, $\cdot\text{NH}_2$, and $\cdot\text{OH}$ and making the approximation that processes (9), (10) and (11) are instantaneous, the following rate expression is arrived at

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+] + k_5[\text{NH}_3][\cdot\text{OH}]$$

Neglecting the second term in the above equation due to a very small value of $[\text{NH}_3]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ in comparison to the first term, the rate expression approximates to

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+]$$

where k_1 is the experimental first order rate constant. The above equation, though in conformity with the general kinetic behaviour, does not explain the observed dependence of the specific rate on the initial concentration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and of propionamide. Evidently the mechanism of Levitt and Milinowski¹¹ for alcohol oxidation given to account for the dependence of specific rate on the concentration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and the organic substrate does not seem to be correct, which has also been questioned by Wiberg¹² on the basis of his tracer studies.

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